

Design and Implementation of An Employee Monitoring System In Lasu Epe Campus, Lagos State University

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ABSTRACT

The employee monitoring system is an android application used to monitor the call logs, sent and receive messages and the GPS location of an employee. The application is implemented using Java script, the application interface was designed with Xml and Php for the automatic mailing system. The organisations success depends on employees' performance; poor performance is detrimental to the company's success. It is necessary for an employer to keep track of his employees' at all times to ensure the quality of service from the employees' and maximum output from them. This paper deals with the design and development of an employee monitoring system using Android which will be accessed from the company's email account.

Keyword: Employee, Monitoring, Android, Mobile Application, JavaScript

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, mobile phones are being used greatly and new technologies emerge from time to time to meet the demands of users. In this project the android platform will be used as it is an open source which is gaining ground in today's market rapidly and is widely accepted and easily accessible in today's market

The employee monitoring system (EMS) is an application which will run on any android mobile phone which has a GPS connectivity. The application will be a background application which will not disturb the functionability of the phone and will not prompt the user for any kind of confirmation.

The purpose of this proposed system is to help the employer or supervisors keep track of its employees Android mobile phone from time to time by monitoring his/her call details, messages and geographical location. The application is installed on the employees' mobile phone and information of the employees activities will be sent to the employer through emails to the employer/supervisor after monitoring the employees' activities.

This application will ensure that the employer will be constantly updated of the dealings of its employees from time to time because the success of an organization depends on the performance of its employees. This will ensure quality of service, detect misuse of company phones and also reduce call charges

METHODOLOGY

The design and implementation of the employee monitoring system adhere to the rules of software requirements analysis; Design, Code generation, Testing, Implementation and support.

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION TECHNIQUES

The Employee monitoring system is an Android application which will monitor all the call records, sent and received messages as well as the GPS location of the user. It was developed using and implemented using these tools;

JavaScript- Dynamic client side scripting language that response to users' events. Javascript is very loosely based on Java, an object oriented programming language popularized for use on web by way of embedded applets. Although JavaScript has a similar syntax and programming methodology, it is not a "light" version of Java. Instead javascript is its own dynamic language, finding its home in web browsers around the world and enabling enhanced user interaction on web sites and web applications alike.

Php - (personal home page) now known as hypertext processor. A dynamic server side scripting language. PHP code is interpreted (not compiled) by a web server with a PHP processor module, which generates the resulting web page: PHP commands can be embedded directly into an HTML source document rather than calling an external file to process data. IT has also evolved to include a command line interface capability and can be used in standalone graphical applications.

Windows operating system – This system is developed and deployed on a windows operating system

ANDROID - Android is a Linux-based operating system for mobile devices such as Smartphones and tablet computers. It is developed by the open handset alliance, led by Google, and other companies

Xml – (Extensive markup language) is a markup language that defines a set of rules for encoding documents in a format which is both human-readable and machine-readable. It is defined by the W3C's XML 1.0 specification and by several other related specifications, all of which are free open standards. The design goals of XML emphasize simplicity, generality and usability across the internet. It is a textual data format with strong support via Unicode for different human languages. Although the design of XML focuses on documents, it is widely used for the representation of arbitrary data structures such as those used in web services.

SYSTEM DESIGN

This system features an android application which will contain the employees' id which will be sent to the companies' email address via the automated mailing system. The application the call logs, inbox and sent messages, and the location of each user to the companies email on a time basis. The calls and messages will be sent every 4 hours while the location will be sent every 2 hours. The model of android the application will run on is Android 4.0 and above.

EMS design flow chart

The application will request from the user device access before installation

Registration page

After installation, the user will be required to provide a unique employee ID. Each user will have a unique ID, for example in the format employee@devcoyote.com.

EMPLOYERS PAGE

The employer will be required to log in to the companies' email which can be accessible from any device, to view the activities of the staffs. When he logs in, he will have the option to view each staffs missed calls, received calls, call logs and location which was sent to the mail. He can decide which employee details he wants to view and time through the companies email.

Employee details forwarded to companies email

Call logs: The email below shows the call logs of the employee, with username Kitty@devcoyote.com after some hours showing the incoming and outgoing calls their durations. The call records will be updated in the next mail sent to the employee if a call activity is made by the employee and will be sent every 4 hours.

Call records of the employee sent to companies email

Sent messages: The email below shows the messages sent to the companies email account with the date and recipient of the message being sent to in the email. This mail will be sent every 4 hours as long as the application is running on the employees android phone and internet connectivity is available

Sent messages by the employee forwarded to companies email

Received messages: This mail shows the messages received by the employee. These mails will be forwarded to the companies email address which can be accessed by the employer on any device. The messages will be forwarded to the companies emails every 4 hours as long as there is internet connectivity on the employees android phone and the application is running

Received messages by the employee forwarded to companies email

GPS location: This email shows the GPS location of the employee, the location is made available through Google map. The GPS connectivity must be turned on for the location of the employee to be determined. The email will be sent every 2 hours as a users' location is subject to change. The user is in Ikeja, Lagos according to the map below

GPS location of an employee in Ikeja, Lagos

CONCLUSION

This application enables the managers to update the overall performance of the employees in their respective areas. This monitoring system is a revolutionary mobile application which uses Android OS for monitoring incoming call details, outgoing call details, messages, email, web history and location. There is no need of manual entering of the daily activity details of each employee onto the database. It completely abolishes the traditional way of calculating performances. This will considerably reduce the paperwork and save ones precious time. This application makes good use of the recent mobile development technologies and thereby increases the overall performance of the employees

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